

North West European Shelf Production Centre NWSHELF_ANALYSISFORECAST_BGC_004_002

Issue: 4.2

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Approval date by the CMEMS product quality coordination team: 29/04/2021

<p>QUID for NWS MFC Products</p> <p>NWSHELF_ANALYSISFORECAST_BGC_004_002</p>	<p>Ref: CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-002</p> <p>Date: 07 January 2021</p> <p>Issue: 4.2</p>
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CHANGE RECORD

When the quality of the products changes, the Quid is updated and a row is added to this table. The third column specifies which sections or sub-sections have been updated. The fourth column should mention the version of the product to which the change applies.

Issue	Date	§	Description of Change	Author	Validated By
1.0	16/09/2011	all	First version of document		
2.0	28/10/2011	all	Updated version of document		
2.1	18/11/2011	V, VI	Minor corrections	A. Sellar	
3.0	15/12/2014	All	New version for MyOcean V5.0 product upgrade	A. McLaren et al.	Ed Blockley
3.1	26/02/2015	All	Revision after V5 acceptance	A. McLaren et al.	Ed Blockley
3.2	May 1 2015	all	Change format to fit CMEMS graphical rules		L. Crosnier
3.3	20/01/2016	I.2, I.3, III.3, IV.6-IV.7	Revision for V2 (MLD and bottom temperature validation)	P. Sykes	M. Tonani
3.3	01/04/2016	I.3, IV.4, IV.6, VI	Revision after CMEMS V2 Acceptance	P. Sykes and M. Tonani	M. Tonani
3.4	6/01/2017		NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHYS-004-001_b moved to a different document..	M. Tonani	M. Tonani
4.0	10/09/2019	all	Revision for V10	S. Kay	M. Tonani
4.1	10/09/2020	all	Revision for V11	R. McEwan	M. Tonani
4.2	07/01/2021	all	Product name updated	I. Ascione	M. Tonani

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I EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

I.1 Products covered by this document

This document refers to the following real-time CMEMS products:

NORTHWESTSHELF_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_BIO_004_002b: The biogeochemical parts of a North West European Shelf Analysis performed at ~7 km resolution.

Table 1 List of NWS-MetOffice BIO variables

Variable	Vertical resolution	Horizontal resolution	Temporal resolution
Chlorophyll	All levels, surface to bottom	7 km	Daily average
Nitrate	All levels, surface to bottom	7 km	Daily average
Phosphate	All levels, surface to bottom	7 km	Daily average
Oxygen	All levels, surface to bottom	7 km	Daily average
Light attenuation	All levels, surface to bottom	7 km	Daily average
pH	All levels, surface to bottom	7 km	Daily average
Partial pressure of CO2	Surface level	7 km	Daily average
Net primary production*	All levels, surface to bottom	7 km	Daily average
Phytoplankton biomass*	All levels, surface to bottom	7 km	Daily average

* For net primary production and phytoplankton biomass, seasonal plots for the current product and the previous version are given, but no quality information is included.

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I.2 Summary of the results

The quality of the North West Shelf analysis and forecast system NWSHELF_ANALYSISFORECAST_BGC_004_002 has been assessed by comparison to observations using a two-year test run (2018-2019). Observational datasets used for comparison include satellite ocean colour chlorophyll and light attenuation, the North Sea Biogeochemistry Climatology, which is based on in situ measurements, gridded measurements from the SOCAT and GLODAP datasets and the ICES database of in situ measurements for 2018-2019 (see below for references, section IV). Values from the previous version of this product have also been included for comparison. This version uses assimilation of satellite chlorophyll values, leading to large changes in some variables, particularly chlorophyll and net primary production.

Chlorophyll: temporal and spatial patterns of chlorophyll distribution at all depths are well reproduced, but the model outputs tend to be lower than observation, especially in winter. Accuracy varies between regions and seasons, but median absolute difference (MAD) in surface log-chlorophyll compared to satellite are typically around 0.26 in the winter and 0.17 in the summer for on-shelf areas. Accuracy is a little lower off-shelf.

Nitrate and phosphate: temporal and spatial patterns of surface nitrate and phosphate distribution match those in a climatology of in situ data. The concentration values are generally in line with in situ, although in the Southern North Sea the nitrate values are generally higher than in situ in the July to September period. Some statistical comparisons have been made, but these should be used with caution, given the relatively low number of observations available, and it is not recommended to use them as Estimated Accuracy Numbers.

Dissolved oxygen: surface oxygen values are underestimated compared to in situ values in most regions, but spatial patterns are well reproduced. Across all depths, oxygen values are overestimated in shallow areas such as the southern North Sea but underestimated elsewhere.

Partial pressure of CO₂ at the surface: seasonal patterns of pCO₂ broadly match those seen in in situ data, with higher values in winter and in coastal areas. Spring values are overestimated compared to in situ observations.

pH: the spatial distribution and size of the surface pH values are in line with a global climatology.

Light attenuation coefficient: values are higher than in a comparable satellite product (Kd490), but shows the same spatial and temporal patterns.

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I.3 Estimated Accuracy Numbers

Surface log-chlorophyll accuracy, based on the match to daily ocean colour satellite values:

Table 2 Estimated accuracy numbers for surface log10-chlorophyll, chlorophyll units mg m⁻³

Region	Median bias		Median absolute difference (MAD)	
	winter	summer	winter	summer
Continental shelf	-0.21	-0.12	0.26	0.17
Full domain	-0.09	-0.03	0.24	0.16

The ocean colour data is taken from the CMEMS catalogue, product OCEANCOLOUR_ATL_CHL_L4_REP_OBSERVATIONS_009_098, 1998-2019. The mean bias of the log-transformed data is -0.02 and the root mean square difference 0.38 (from the product QUID).

The following table shows estimated median bias (model-observation) and median absolute difference for the on-shelf part of the model domain, based on match-ups to in situ observations. **The estimates should be used with caution:** the in situ measurements are not distributed evenly in time or space and their accuracy is not known. Users are advised to consult the tables in section IV for more information about accuracy within each region: there is considerable variation between regions. EANs are given only for chlorophyll and oxygen, because there was insufficient in situ data available for other products.

Table 3 Estimated accuracy numbers for NWS BIO variables

Variable	Median bias (model-observation)	Median absolute difference	Units	Decimal places
Chlorophyll-a	-0.3	0.6	mg m ⁻³	1
Dissolved oxygen	3.4	12.2	mmol m ⁻³	1

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II PRODUCTION SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Production centres name:

Met Office, UK

Production system name:

Met Office – FOAM Shelf Seas Atlantic Margin Model 7 km (AMM7)

Description

The North West Shelf analysis and forecast is produced using the Forecasting Ocean Assimilation Model 7 km Atlantic Margin model (FOAM AMM7) which is comprised of version 3.6 of the Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean (NEMO) ocean model code (Madec et al., 2016) coupled to the European Regional Seas Ecosystem Model (ERSEM 19.04; Butenschön et al. 2016). This version of the system incorporates data assimilation of surface chlorophyll from the CMEMS product OCEANCOLOUR_ATL_CHL_L3_NRT_OBSERVATIONS_009_036.

The model is located on the European North-West continental Shelf (NWS), from 40°N, 20°W to 65°N, 13°E (boundary region masked), on a regular lat-lon grid with 1/15° latitudinal resolution and 1/9° longitudinal resolution (approximately 7 km square). The model domain is shown in Figure 1, partitioned into shallow (on shelf) and deeper (off shelf) waters. Although the domain extends beyond the shelf to include some of the adjacent North-East Atlantic, the focus of this system is on the shelf itself and the deep water is primarily included to ensure there is appropriate cross-shelf exchange. Thus a hybrid s-sigma terrain following coordinate system (following Siddorn and Furner, 2013) with 51 levels is employed in order to retain vertical resolution on the shelf. However, in order to make analysis and visualization easier for users, the products are delivered on 24 geopotential (z-level) vertical levels based upon the ICES standard depths. Gridpoints near to the model boundaries are strongly affected by the boundary conditions and so products are provided for the interior of the domain only. The outermost 10 gridpoints and points East of 10°E on the Baltic boundary are masked.

Figure 1 FOAM AMM7 bathymetry showing (left) the domain on the European North West Shelf (defined here as total depth less than 200m) and (right) the domain off the shelf.

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ERSEM is a marine biogeochemistry model which simultaneously describes pelagic and benthic ecosystems in terms of phytoplankton, bacteria, zooplankton, zoobenthos and the biogeochemical cycling of C, N, P and Si. ERSEM uses a functional group approach to describe the ecosystem, whereby biota are grouped together according to their trophic level (subdivided according to first size, then trophic role and finally feeding method). Four functional groups of phytoplankton are included, three of zooplankton and one of bacteria. The dynamics of biological functional groups are described by both physiological (ingestion, respiration, excretion and egestion) and population processes (growth and mortality). The differences between the functional groups mainly lie in the rate constants, which are derived from the literature or from allometric considerations and in the food components on the uptake side. Production of the phytoplankton groups is driven by broadband photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), and underwater light field computed with the Beer-Lambert equation of light attenuation.

The version of ERSEM, 19.04, also has the following features:

- It includes the carbonate system, enabling pCO₂ and pH to be included in the available products.
- The diffuse attenuation coefficient is computed by using broadband absorption and backscattering (i.e. the “Inherent Optical Properties”) of the phytoplankton groups, of water, and of coloured detrital matter and other non-modelled material; the latter is nudged towards climatological satellite data. Suspended particulate matter is not explicitly included in the model.
- The model parameters match those given by Butenschön et al. (2016).
- ERSEM is coupled to the NEMO physical model through the Framework for Aquatic Biogeochemical Models (FABM, Bruggeman and Bolding, 2014), which gives greater flexibility. However, this layer is not visible to the end user.

Full information on ERSEM can be found in Butenschön et al. (2016) and references therein. Version 19.04 has only minor changes since the 15.06 version described by Butenschön et al. (2016): pH is now provided on total scale instead of seawater scale and there are changes to handling of particulate matter at the sea bed.

The ecosystem model uses climatologies for the biogeochemical boundary conditions and river inputs. Boundary values of nitrate, phosphate, silicate and oxygen are from World Ocean Atlas 2013v2 (WOA, Garcia et al., 2014a,b); alkalinity and dissolved inorganic carbon from GLODAPv2 (Key et al., 2015, and Lauvset et al., 2016) and river nutrient concentrations from a daily climatology compiled for the purpose. Nitrogen deposition at the surface uses the last available year from the EMEP project (<http://www.emep.int>). The ecosystem model is forced by the physical model via an online coupling and is run at the same time step as the physical model (300s).

This version of the system differs from the previous in that assimilation of surface chlorophyll data has been added, using the NEMOVAR (Mogensen et al. 2009, 2012; Waters et al. 2015, King et al., 2018) 3DVAR assimilation scheme. The method is as described in Skákala et al. (2018) for total surface chlorophyll concentration, except for minor differences in the treatment of observation error and correlation length scales used. The data used in the assimilation is total chlorophyll concentrations from CMEMS Product OCEANCOLOUR_ATL_CHL_L3_NRT_OBSERVATIONS_009_036, specifically dataset-oc-atl-chl-multi_cci-l3-chl_1km_daily-rt-v02. A first guess at appropriate time technique is used to produce the differences between observations and the model. Model matchups are produced with bilinear interpolation to observation locations at midday. NEMOVAR calculates increments to total chlorophyll at each surface grid point. Increments to all model phytoplankton variables are then

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calculated from these and applied throughout the mixed layer, so as to maintain the existing ratios at each model grid point between phytoplankton functional types, and the stoichiometric ratios of chlorophyll, C, N, P, and Si within each phytoplankton type.

Physical variables from this modelling system are provided in product NWSHELF_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_LR_004_001. For full details of that system, its forcing data and product quality please see its Quality Information Document (CMEMS-NWS-QUID-004-001-b.pdf).

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III VALIDATION FRAMEWORK

The products assessed are chlorophyll, nitrate, phosphate, oxygen, pCO₂, pH and light attenuation.

Model surface chlorophyll is compared to daily satellite ocean colour measurements (CMEMS product OCEANCOLOUR_ATL_CHL_L4_REP_OBSERVATIONS_009_098) to give seasonal maps for the whole domain and time series plots and statistics for sub-regions.

Model nutrients and oxygen are compared to climatological fields from the North Sea Biogeochemical Climatology (Hinrichs et al., 2017) to give seasonal maps of surface values.

Time series of surface chlorophyll and nitrate are compared to in situ measurements from the Western Channel Observatory (point L4; 50°15.0'N, 4°13.0'W, www.westernchannelobservatory.org.uk, **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**).

Surface pCO₂ is compared to seasonal averages of the SOCATv2019 gridded coastal fields for 2000-2019, taken from CMEMS product INSITU_GLO_CARBON_REP_OBSERVATIONS_013_050.

Surface pH is compared to the annual average GLODAP gridded field, taken from CMEMS product INSITU_GLO_CARBON_REP_OBSERVATIONS_013_050.

The light attenuation coefficient is compared to daily satellite ocean colour measurements of Kd490 (OCEANCOLOUR_GLO_OPTICS_L3_REP_OBSERVATIONS_009_086) to give seasonal maps for the whole domain and time series plots and statistics for sub-regions.

All assessed variables except pCO₂ and light attenuation have been compared to in situ measurements at all depths from the database of the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES, 2014). This comparison has been used to produce Estimated Accuracy Numbers for chlorophyll and dissolved oxygen, but for other variables there are too few observations available for a quantitative assessment to be made.

Robust statistics have been used for the comparison to satellite products and in situ observations. These are independent of the distribution of the data and so avoid distortion by outliers. Metrics used are:

Number of matched observations (n) All metrics are based on the set of observations and a set of model outputs matched in time and space. In situ observations were matched to the daily mean model outputs: a match was considered valid if it was in the same grid cell, within 10 m vertically and 1 day of the observation. Observations are sparse in some areas, the number of matched points is shown in the tables in section IV and quantitative information is only given where the number and distribution of observations was sufficient to give a meaningful summary.

Median Bias: the median of the difference between the model data and the observation (reference) data. This gives an indication of consistent differences between the model and observation, with positive bias meaning the model is higher than observation.

$$Bias = median(x_{model} - x_{reference})$$

Median absolute difference (MAD): the median of the absolute difference between the model and observation values at each point. This indicates the average size of the difference between model and observation.

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$$MAD = median(abs(x_{model} - x_{reference}))$$

Spearman rank correlation coefficient: this is the Pearson correlation coefficient between the ranked values of the model and observation data: if the model data increases when the observations do, they are positively correlated. It can be interpreted in the same way as the Pearson correlation, i.e. 1 shows perfect correlation and 0 shows no correlation.

Statistics have been calculated for the whole model domain and for various subregions – see Figure 2 for the location of these regions.

Regions:

EC: English Channel

IS: Irish Sea

NNS: Northern North Sea

NT: Norwegian Trench

NWA: North Western Approaches

SNS: Southern North Sea

SWA: South Western Approaches

The Continental Shelf regions includes all the above, i.e. all regions except Offshelf.

Observation stations:

L4: station L4 of the Western Channel Observatory

Figure 2 Regions and observing stations referred to in this document.

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IV VALIDATION RESULTS

The product has been evaluated using a two-year test run, for 2018-2019. Results from this analysis are given in the sections below, including a comparison to the previous version.

IV.1 Chlorophyll-a

The chlorophyll-a product has been compared to values from satellite and in situ measurements for the test period (2018-2019).

In Figure 3 the seasonal averages of surface chlorophyll are compared to satellite and in situ data. The satellite data is taken from the CMEMS level 4 daily Globcolour product (OCEANCOLOUR_ATL_CHL_L4_REP_OBSERVATIONS_009_098), and the climatology of in situ data is from the North Sea Biogeochemical Climatology (Hinrichs et al., 2017, https://doi.org/10.1594/WDCC/NSBClim_v1.1). The model reproduces the spatial and temporal variation seen in the observation data well. The satellite product used for this comparison differs from the product being assimilated, however since they share some raw sensor sources, it is expected that the assimilative model will resemble the satellite.

The model-observation differences are larger when the model is compared to the in situ climatology (third row) rather than to satellite values (second row) but the pattern of higher spring values and lower winter is the same. It should be noted that the satellite data is for 2018-2019, as for the model outputs, but the North Sea Biogeochemical Climatology is based on in situ data from 1970-2014, so the comparison is less direct. In particular, river nutrient loads have decreased over that period so values near river mouths may be overestimated.

Chlorophyll distributions and sizes are better in the current product (V11) than the previous one (V10, fourth row). The current product has higher winter chlorophyll and lower spring and summer chlorophyll, because it is constrained by data assimilation while the previous product was not.

Comparison to satellite is also presented using regionally-averaged time series (**Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**) and statistics (Table 4). To produce these, the daily satellite data were interpolated on to the model grid and then matched to the model daily values. Data points missing due to cloud were excluded. The close match of the model and satellite in the growing season is again evident, but this is not the case in the shallower areas (Irish Sea, Southern North Sea and English Channel). Differences from the previous version (V10) vary from region to region, but there is a tendency for the summer peaks to be lower and the spring bloom to start earlier than in V10.

Summary statistics have been calculated for both winter and summer (Table 4), with autumn and spring having intermediate values. The performance of V11 is better than V10 in most regions and seasons; broadly speaking V11 has smaller bias and median absolute difference (MAD) and higher correlation, especially in the summer.

Figure 3 Seasonal average surface chlorophyll-a from (top row) the current product V11 (second row) ocean colour satellite, CMEMS level 4 product 009_098 (third row) climatology from the North Sea Biogeochemical Climatology in situ dataset (bottom row) the previous model version V10.

Figure 4 Time series of daily surface chlorophyll for regions of the North West Shelf, from the current product (V11), the previous version (V10) and ocean colour satellite (CMEMS_OC_009_098). See Figure 2 for the location of the regions.

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Table 4 Statistics for match-ups between daily model surface log-chlorophyll outputs and satellite ocean colour chlorophyll for the full domain and sub-regions. See Figure 2 for the location of the regions. The Continental shelf includes all regions except Offshelf.

Region	Current product (V11)						Previous product (V10)					
	median bias (log(mg m ⁻³))		MAD (log(mg m ⁻³))		Spearman correlation coefficient		median bias (log(mg m ⁻³))		MAD (log(mg m ⁻³))		Spearman correlation coefficient	
	winter	summer	winter	summer	winter	summer	winter	summer	winter	summer	winter	summer
Full Domain	-0.09	-0.03	0.24	0.16	0.52	0.73	-1.79	0.37	1.79	0.42	0.58	0.48
Continental shelf	-0.21	-0.12	0.26	0.17	0.57	0.77	-1.56	0.22	1.56	0.29	0.60	0.51
Offshelf	-0.03	0.01	0.24	0.15	0.33	0.71	-1.90	0.43	1.90	0.48	0.47	0.48
Norwegian Trench	-0.47	-0.09	0.56	0.15	0.47	0.65	-1.89	0.26	1.89	0.32	0.58	0.52
Northern North Sea	-0.83	-0.07	0.86	0.14	0.61	0.64	-2.38	0.36	2.38	0.37	0.71	0.48
Southern North Sea	-0.24	-0.23	0.26	0.24	0.49	0.81	-1.06	0.06	1.06	0.23	0.34	0.42
English Channel	-0.09	-0.19	0.12	0.19	0.63	0.73	-0.61	0.07	0.69	0.17	0.47	0.34
Irish Sea	-0.37	-0.15	0.38	0.19	0.48	0.55	-1.49	0.01	1.49	0.22	0.46	0.38
South Western Approaches	-0.08	-0.07	0.12	0.13	0.70	0.81	-1.54	0.16	1.54	0.26	0.31	0.57
North Western Approaches	-0.40	-0.02	0.47	0.16	0.48	0.58	-1.62	0.47	1.62	0.48	0.50	0.33

A time series of in situ chlorophyll measurements for 2018 is available for station L4 in the western English Channel (Figure 2) and this is presented in Figure 5. The current product matches the in situ data well, although the magnitude of the spring bloom is underestimated the timing is reproduced well.

Figure 5 Time series of model, satellite and in situ surface chlorophyll concentration (mg m⁻³) from station L4. V11 is the current product, V10 the previous version, ocean colour is from CMEMS product 009_098. See Figure 2 for the location of L4.

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Statistics from match-ups of model chlorophyll outputs at all depths to in situ observations from the ICES database are given in Table 5, for regions where there was enough observational data for a meaningful comparison. The bias values are averages for all the times when the observations were made and therefore lack the seasonal information included in Table 4: they should be used with caution. The MAD values, showing the median difference between model and observation, show considerable variation between regions but the whole-domain value of 0.6 mg m^{-3} is probably a reasonable estimate for the dataset as a whole. Correlation is good in all regions, giving confidence in the spatial distribution estimated by the model. Model performance is broadly improved compared with V10, with a slightly reduced MAD in most regions.

Table 5 Statistics for match-ups between daily model chlorophyll outputs and in situ observations from the ICES database (ICES, 2014), for selected sub-regions. See section III for information on the match-up process and statistics provided and the locations of the regions.

Region	number of observations	V11			V10		
		bias (mg m^{-3})	MAD (mg m^{-3})	Corr	bias (mg m^{-3})	MAD (mg m^{-3})	Corr
Continental shelf	2154	-0.27	0.60	0.64	-0.27	1.04	0.39
Northern North Sea	202	-0.35	0.37	0.47	-0.39	0.40	-0.04
Southern North Sea	715	-0.81	1.20	0.62	-0.87	1.44	0.53

Figure 6 shows model forecast surface chlorophyll concentration for the Continental shelf (top), English Channel (middle) and L4 buoy (bottom) as well as the Globcolour satellite chlorophyll product (OCEANCOLOUR_ATL_CHL_L4_REP_OBSERVATIONS_009_098). The strong effect of data assimilation is clear as successive daily forecast values quickly diverge from the satellite product during the productive spring and summer months.

These plots highlight the importance of considering appropriate spatial and temporal scales when assessing model performance. The orange line in the top two plots shows the number of grid point matchups for the series. The winter dip in matchups for the Continental shelf region is a result of loss of satellite coverage in the northern part of the domain. These periods also see an increase in ocean colour error (pink shaded region) and negative forecast bias. The timing and magnitude of peak satellite chlorophyll concentrations differ in the 3 plots with L4 showing a period of high production in autumn 2018 that isn't clear in the larger region averages.

At the shelf scale chlorophyll concentration forecasts are higher than observations during the spring with overprediction increasing with forecast lead time. In winter the opposite is true although there is a smaller proportional increase in error with lead time.

Figure 6 Timeseries of surface chlorophyll concentration for (top) continental shelf average, (middle) English Channel average, (bottom) station L4. Day 0 is the analysis day, with assimilation of satellite chlorophyll, and days 1-6 are forecast days. Satellite ocean colour values are shown in red for comparison.

IV.2 Nitrate

In Figure 7 the seasonal averages of surface nitrate are compared to the climatology of in situ data from the North Sea Biogeochemical Climatology (Hinrichs et al., 2017, https://doi.org/10.1594/WDCC/NSBClim_v1.1). The current product (V11) generally reproduces well the spatial and temporal patterns seen in the climatology, and levels are similar to the previous product (V10). The assimilation of chlorophyll reduces phytoplankton biomass during the summer and increases it in the winter, which has an effect on nutrients. Compared to climatology (Figure 7) and in situ measurements from L4 (Figure 8) the current product doesn't reproduce the lowest nitrate concentrations of summer but better matches the winter regeneration. The main differences are seen in the Southern North Sea, where the model values show less seasonal variability than in situ.

The North Sea Biogeochemical Climatology is based on in situ data from 1970-2014 and river nutrient loads have decreased over that period so the in situ values may be overestimated in areas affected by river inputs, such as the German Bight.

Figure 7 Seasonal average surface nitrate from (top row) the current product V11 (second row) climatology from the North Sea Biogeochemical Climatology in situ dataset (bottom row) the previous version of the product V10.

Figure 8 shows a comparison of model outputs of surface nitrate to a time series of in situ data from station L4 in the western English Channel (Figure 2). The seasonal pattern of nitrate variation is broadly captured by the model, with high winter values of $\sim 7 \text{ mmol m}^{-3}$ dropping quickly to low values in April-May. However the autumn rise occurs several weeks earlier in the model than in the in situ measurements and the spring fall is a little delayed. The current product, V11, shows a smaller seasonal variation than the previous version (V10) and lower peak values, however winter values are closer to the in situ than V10.

Figure 8 Time series of model and in situ surface nitrate concentration (mmol m^{-3}) from station L4. V11 is the current product, V10 the previous version. See Figure 2 for the location of L4.

Statistics from match-ups of model nitrate outputs to observations from the ICES database are given in Table 6, for regions where there was enough observational data for a meaningful comparison. These should be used with caution, given the relatively low number of observations available, and it is not recommended to use them as Estimated Accuracy Numbers. The overestimation of nitrate, seen in Figure 7, is also evident here; most of the observations in this region are from coastal areas where the influence of river inputs is relatively strong. Based on these statistics the performance of the V11 version is an improvement on the V10; these changes are due to some adjustments in river input values and the effect of chlorophyll data assimilation..

Table 6 Statistics for match-ups between daily model nitrate outputs and in situ observations from the ICES database (ICES, 2014), for selected sub-regions. See section III for information on the match-up process and statistics provided and the locations of the regions.

Region	number of observations	V11			V10		
		bias (mmol m^{-3})	MAD (mmol m^{-3})	Corr	bias (mmol m^{-3})	MAD (mmol m^{-3})	Corr
Continental shelf	1553	3.46	3.89	0.47	6.40	6.76	0.42
Northern North Sea	441	0.29	0.98	0.55	4.22	3.80	0.40
Southern	428	20.12	16.96	0.33	32.75	26.22	0.25

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IV.3 Phosphate

In Figure 9 the seasonal averages of surface phosphate are compared to the climatology of in situ data from the North Sea Biogeochemical Climatology (Hinrichs et al., 2017, https://doi.org/10.1594/WDC/NSBClim_v1.1). The current product generally reproduces well the spatial and temporal patterns seen in the climatology, although concentrations on the shelf are lower throughout the year, whilst the previous product (V10) is generally higher. These changes are due to some adjustments in river input values and the effect of chlorophyll data assimilation. The North Sea Biogeochemical Climatology is based on in situ data from 1970-2014 and river nutrient loads have decreased over that period so the in situ values may be overestimated in areas affected by river inputs, such as the German Bight.

Figure 9 Seasonal average surface phosphate from (top row) the current product V11 (second row) climatology from the North Sea Biogeochemical Climatology in situ dataset (bottom row) the previous version of the product V10.

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Statistics from match-ups of model phosphate outputs to observations from the ICES database have been calculated for V11 and V10. The analysis shows that the V11 and V10 versions have broadly similar correlations, but with V11 slightly underestimating phosphate whereas V10 overestimates by a larger amount. The median absolute difference is lower for version 11. Table 7 shows values for regions where there was enough observational data for a meaningful comparison. These should be used with caution, given the relatively low number of observations available, and it is not recommended to use them as Estimated Accuracy Numbers.

Table 7 Statistics for match-ups between daily model phosphate outputs and in situ observations from the ICES database (ICES, 2014), for selected sub-regions. See section III for information on the match-up process and statistics provided and the locations of the regions.

Region	number of observations	V11			V10		
		bias (mmol m ⁻³)	MAD (mmol m ⁻³)	Corr	bias (mmol m ⁻³)	MAD (mmol m ⁻³)	Corr
Continental shelf	1682	-0.09	0.16	0.53	0.30	0.26	0.42
Northern North Sea	440	-0.15	0.17	0.52	0.19	0.18	0.51
Southern North Sea	528	-0.01	0.20	0.41	0.85	0.87	0.28

IV.4 Dissolved Oxygen

In Figure 10 the seasonal averages of surface oxygen are compared to the climatology of in situ data from the North Sea Biogeochemical Climatology (Hinrichs et al., 2017, https://doi.org/10.1594/WDCC/NSBClim_v1.1). The current product tends to underestimate surface oxygen compared to the in situ values, especially in the winter, but spatial patterns of variation are well reproduced, including higher values in the far north and a summer low in the Southern North Sea.

The North Sea Biogeochemical Climatology is based on in situ data from 1970-2014 and sea surface temperatures have risen during and since that period, leading to lower oxygen solubility in recent years. Therefore it is likely that this climatology overestimates dissolved oxygen compared to present-day values.

Statistics from match-ups of model oxygen outputs at all depths to observations from the ICES database are given in Table 8, for regions where there was enough observational data for a meaningful comparison. Model bias is negative in most regions, consistent with the underestimation of oxygen seen in Figure 10, but positive in the southern North Sea.

Figure 10 Seasonal average surface dissolved oxygen from (top row) the current product (second row) climatology from the North Sea Biogeochemical in situ dataset (bottom row) the previous product.

Table 8 Statistics for match-ups between daily model oxygen outputs and in situ observations from the ICES database (ICES, 2014), for selected sub-regions. See section III for information on the match-up process and statistics provided and the locations of the regions.

Region	number of observations	V11			V10		
		bias (mmol m ⁻³)	MAD (mmol m ⁻³)	Corr	bias (mmol m ⁻³)	MAD (mmol m ⁻³)	Corr
Continental shelf	23032	3.4	12.2	0.61	1.01	12.66	0.68
Norwegian Trench	5837	-3.2	15.1	0.64	-12.42	19.21	0.78
Northern North Sea	4839	-12.0	14.4	0.64	-16.05	16.03	0.87
Southern North Sea	10186	7.4	10.6	0.70	5.84	9.20	0.71

IV.5 Surface pCO₂

The modelled surface partial pressure of CO₂ (pCO₂) was compared to in situ data from the SOCAT v2019 database (Bakker et al., 2016), CMEMS product INSITU_GLO_CARBON_REP_OBSERVATIONS_013_050. The SOCAT values are for fugacity of CO₂, but the difference between fugacity and partial pressure is small in the conditions of this region.

Figure 11 shows seasonal mean fields from the current product (V11) and seasonal averages of the monthly values in the SOCAT gridded coastal dataset. SOCAT values from years before 2000 were not used, to reduce the effect of the increase in atmospheric CO₂ concentrations during the observation period. The SOCAT dataset gives incomplete coverage, but the same broad patterns can be seen in the model and in situ data, with higher values in winter and in coastal areas. Spring values appear lower in SOCAT than the model outputs.

There is an improvement from the previous product (V10) which had too high pCO₂ in winter and too low in summer compared to the SOCAT data.

Figure 11 Seasonal average surface pCO₂ from (top row) the current product V11 (second row) mean values from the SOCAT v2019 gridded coastal observation dataset (bottom row) the previous version of the product V10.

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IV.6 pH

Figure 12 shows annual mean surface fields from the current product (V11) and the gridded GLODAP dataset (1972-2013), taken from CMEMS product INSITU_GLO_CARBON_REP_OBSERVATIONS_013_050. The spatial patterns and size of the modelled pH broadly matches GLODAP – for example, lower values in the southern North Sea – but the relatively low resolution of the GLODAP product limits the possible comparison.

Comparison to in situ data suggests that model outputs have little bias but relatively high error, however there is too little observational data available for a quantitative comparison.

The V10 product has a higher average pH than the V11 but both show similar patterns of spatial variability.

Figure 12 Annual average surface pH from (left) the current product (centre) the GLODAP gridded in situ dataset (right) the previous version of the product.

IV.7 Light attenuation

Figure 13 shows the seasonal average attenuation coefficient at the surface for the current and previous versions of the model and also for satellite-derived values for Kd490 (which is a comparable but not identical measure of attenuation, Kd490 refers to attenuation at 490 nm, while the model has no spectral dependence). The current product V11 presents slightly lower values than V10 for all regions.

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Figure 13 Seasonal average surface light attenuation coefficient from (top row) the current product (third row) the previous product. The middle row shows Kd490 derived from ocean colour satellite, CMEMS level 3 product 009_086; this is a comparable but not identical measure of attenuation.

IV.8 Net primary production and phytoplankton biomass

No observation data was available for these products but seasonal plots are included so that users can assess the spatial temporal patterns and the difference between the current product (V11) and the previous one (V10).

Net primary production (Figure 14) is highest in the spring and very low in the autumn and winter. Production is generally lower in V11 than in V10, related to the decrease in chlorophyll values due to the introduction of data assimilation. The differences are largest especially off the shelf and close to the coast. Phytoplankton biomass (Figure 15) follows similar trends, as would be expected.

Figure 14 Seasonal average modelled net primary production at the sea surface, from the current product (V11) and the previous one (V10).

Figure 15 Seasonal average modelled phytoplankton biomass at the sea surface, from the current product (V11) and the previous one (V10).

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V SYSTEM'S NOTICEABLE EVENTS, OUTAGES OR CHANGES

Date	Change/Event description	System version	other
Dec 2020	Addition of Chlorophyll data assimilation	AMM7v11	

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VI QUALITY CHANGES SINCE PREVIOUS VERSION

The introduction of assimilation of satellite chlorophyll and some changes to river inputs have led to an improvement in several aspects of the model.

For surface chlorophyll, the performance of V11 is better than V10 in most regions and seasons. V11 has lower spring and summer chlorophyll in coastal and off-shelf areas, and the spring bloom tends to start a little earlier.

Surface nitrate levels have improved in V11 when compared to climatology, with a general reduction across most regions.

Surface phosphate levels have also reduced in V11, especially in on-shelf regions. Compared to in situ measurements, V11 biases are negative and V10 biases are positive, but overall performance is similar.

Surface dissolved oxygen values are a little lower than in V10, and lower than in a climatology of in situ measurements. Comparison to measurements at all depths shows a more mixed picture and broadly comparable accuracy.

Light attenuation coefficient is lower than in V10 and remains a good match to the spatial patterns seen in a comparable satellite product.

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